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METHODS OF CIVIL SERVANTS' QUALIFICATION UPGRADE

МЕТОДИ ПІДВИЩЕННЯ КВАЛІФІКАЦІЇ ДІЯЛЬНОСТІ ДЕРЖАВНОГО СЛУЖБОВЦЯ

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Граціотова Г.О., Граціотов О.О., Степанова А.В. Методи підвищення кваліфікації діяльності державного службовця. Оглядова стаття.

В даній статті досліджено питання державної служби, надано визначення цього терміну та похідного від нього поняття державного службовця, який є посадовою особою держорганів України. Розглянуто класифікацію видів державної служби за формою діяльності, а також за специфікою компетенцій та повноважень державних органів України. Зазначено основний перелік функцій та завдань, які покладає на себе державна служба та зобов'язується виконувати на користь країни та її населення, виключаючи можливість отримання власної вигоди. Перелічено методи підвищення кваліфікації діяльності державних службовців в Україні, а також розглянуто питання отримання освіти для майбутньої діяльності у державних органах.

Ключові слова: підвищення кваліфікації, державна служба, державний службовець, види держслужби, функції держслужби, навчання державних службовців

Hratsiotova H.O., Hratiotov O.O., Stepanova A.V. Methods of Civil Servants' Qualification Upgrade. Review article.

This article examines the issue of civil service, provides a definition of this term and its derived concept of a civil servant who is an official of public authorities of Ukraine. The classification of civil service types according to the form of activity, as well as according to the specifics of competencies and powers of public authorities of Ukraine is considered. The main list of functions and tasks that the civil service assumes and undertakes to perform for the benefit of the country and its population, excluding the possibility of obtaining their own benefits. The methods of civil servants' qualification upgrade in Ukraine are listed, as well as the issue of obtaining education for future activities in public authorities.

Keywords: qualification upgrade, the civil service, a civil servant, the types of civil service, the civil service functions, civil servants' training

The relevance of the chosen research topic is due to the decline and insufficient level of modern methods development of qualification upgrade in the field of civil servants activity of Ukraine. Among the general reasons that motivate this process improvement one can emphasize the following: increasing the efficiency of public authorities, ensuring clear observance and realization of citizens' rights and freedoms, as well as creating conditions for further development of the civil service in Ukraine. Nowadays, Ukraine, like all other countries is interested in self-improvement and professional experience of the working population, provides opportunities for advanced training for all segments of the population who have the appropriate desire.

Analysis of recent researches and publications

Professional upgrade methods have always been the focus of both the state and scientists. The National Agency of Ukraine for Civil Service Affairs (NACS) has repeatedly initiated informational online sessions on civil servants and local government officials' professional upgrade, the purpose of which was to regulate the civil servants' professional upgrade process and also its organization [1]. In addition, the following researchers and scientists as V. Luhovyi, H. Yermolaieva, N. Lasna, L. Plaksii, O. Khmelevska, A. Pierov, O. Braichenko, M. Orliv, K. Zadoia and others have drawn attention to this issue in their studies.

Unsolved aspects of the problem

Despite the presence of various scientific works of the above-mentioned scientists, the issue of uncertainty of civil servants' professional upgrade methods still remains open and needs more detailed research. The

professional upgrade process has always played a significant role in all specialized areas of society, but in the public sector this problem is most acute, as civil servants' education and awareness directly affect the society and other areas of its activities. Moreover, the population and the country's needs have naturally changed over time, which has also had an impact on civil servants' professional upgrade methods.

The aim of the article is a thorough study of professional upgrade methods in public sector activities, the definition of basic concepts such as the civil service and a civil servant, as well as acquaintance with the variety of the civil service functions and its types. The article aims to clearly delineate the methods of civil servants' training, as well as to explore methods of further improving their professional skills.

The main part

According to the Regulation on the system of training, retraining and professional upgrade of civil servants and local self-government officials, approved by the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine of 7 July 2010 No 564, professional upgrade should be a continuous process. However, the current system of civil servants and local self-government officials' professional upgrade is characterized by the mismatch between the frequency of training and the rapid pace of change and the growing demands on civil servants' professional level; insufficient connection of education with the urgent problems of political, social, economic development that exist in the country; insufficient practical orientation of training. Therefore, one of the priority areas for improving the training system for civil servants and local self-government officials is to ensure their professional growth throughout life. This requires the definition of scientific principles and ways to implement continuing education and appropriate teaching and learning sources development.

The best practices of scientific and theoretical provisions on the personnel training system development for public administration, reforming, organization and functioning of the civil service are basic for the conceptual principles development for reforming civil servants and local self-government officials' professional training system. At the same time, the analysis of modern scientific literature has shown that today there is no mechanism for improving the civil servants and local self-government officials' training system, ensuring its continuity, as well as the foreign experience adaptation in Ukraine. The principles of reforming the vocational training system in this category are considered sporadically, without taking into account the integrated approach.

Therefore, the priority tasks of scientific investigations of the advanced training system are a thorough analysis of the actual status and proposals development for improving the regulatory framework for its operation; strengthening the connection between education and the urgent problems of political, socio-economic development of the country, ensuring its continuity and increasing efficiency; introducing innovative models of professional upgrade and European educational learning technologies.

Today, in the context of implementing the constitutional principles of a democratic, legal, social state and the civil society formation, the issue of improving the staffing of the state apparatus with highly qualified and competent professionals capable of working effectively in public authorities and local self-government bodies. The society and the state need to train a new generation and improve the skills of existing leaders and specialists of public authorities and local self-government bodies, the formation of a real and promising reserve of their staff, to be trained in a timely manner to replace new positions, including in new state apparatus, in order to improve quality and increase efficiency of the management process. Thus, one of the priority areas of socio-economic development of Ukraine is the qualitative development of civil servants' training, retraining and professional upgrade system.

As it is stated in the Law of Ukraine "On Civil Service", the civil service is a professional political activity that provides for public reporting and is aimed at solving problems and fulfilling the tasks and functions assigned to the state [2]. This activity is regulated by law and has defined and clear limits of authority.

The range of tasks assigned to the civil service is quite extensive. This is due to the fact that its impact affects many areas of society that require constant regulation and control. If we talk about the most important assignments of civil service, we should highlight the following [3]:

- protection of the rights and freedoms of Ukraine's citizens listed in the current Constitution of the country;
- protection of the rights and interests of various firms, organizations and enterprises in accordance with the law;
- civil servants' professional upgrade;
- adherence to the public authorities principles, such as publicity, transparency, fairness, legality, etc.;
- management of the state's corporate rights;
- all possible assistance in achieving the goals of higher authorities;
- encouraging the civil servants to apply modern information technologies to automate or speed up work processes;
- minimizing the rapid turnover of regular labour force in the civil service and creating material, financial and social conditions for civil servants' convenient and effective work in Ukraine.

The civil service, like any other, has its own values. The main values of civil service are (fig. 1) [3]:

- security activities in the sphere of the constitutional system of Ukraine;
- implementing various provisions contained in the current Ukrainian Constitution;
- promoting the society's development and creating appropriate conditions for this process;
- creating a basis for public authorities effective and efficient activities;

- professional provision of services within its powers;
- supremacy of the observance principle of the constitutional rights and freedoms of a person and a citizen, promoting their observance and realization.

Figure 1. The Main Values of the Civil Service
Source: compiled by authors on materials [3].

The concept of a civil servant arose on the basis of the concept of the civil service and is derived from it. A civil servant is a person who is a citizen of Ukraine and holds a position in a state body of the country. He/she performs the civil service functions within the allotted powers and competencies, and his/her remuneration comes from the state budget [4].

Article 4 of the Law of Ukraine "On Civil Service" defines a list of principles that must be followed by a civil servant during his/her professional activity [2]. These principles are the fundamental vectors of this activity.

The law supremacy principle is the principle of state power, which determines the supremacy of human rights and freedoms, which are enshrined in the Constitution of Ukraine, over other principles. The state power is aimed at the citizens' constitutional rights realization and in no case should they restrict them in the course of their activities.

The legality principle is a principle of the civil service, which provides for the tasks implementation set before a state body in compliance with the provisions of the Constitution of Ukraine and the laws of Ukraine.

The professionalism principle is a principle of the civil service, which provides for the availability of professional skills and knowledge of a civil servant, as well as the constant improvement of his/her skills and abilities.

The patriotism principle is a principle of the civil service, which provides for the civil servants awareness' of the need for dedicated service for the benefit of the state and the Ukrainian people.

The integrity principle is a principle of the civil service, which provides for a civil servant's devotion to the sphere of his/her activity and the direction of his/her actions and powers in favour of public rather than private (own) interests.

The efficiency principle is a principle of the civil service, which notes the need to use all means within reach to achieve the goal.

The principle of ensuring equal access to the civil service is a principle of the civil service, which emphasizes all citizens' equality when entering the civil service and eliminates any discrimination in this matter.

The political impartiality principle is a principle of the civil service that emphasizes the need to remain politically neutral in dealing with any public and professional issues by a civil servant.

The transparency principle is a principle of the civil service, which provides for publicity and openness of civil servants, except when otherwise stated in the laws or the Constitution of Ukraine

Every civil servant must be professionally experienced in the field of his/her activity and his/her education level must correspond to the position he/she holds. The citizen who holds a civil servant's position until the end of his/her service is obliged to take timely measures to improve his/her skills, as well as re-certification within the period specified by law. Another feature of a civil servant is possessing the information that is a special and direct subject of his/her work, which allows him/her to influence the subordinate staff and people who request this information.

As each civil servant has a different amount of skills and powers, there is a classification according to the nature of the job functions they perform. This classification distinguishes:

- managers,
 - specialists;
 - service personnel, which in turn is divided into support and technical.
- In addition, civil servants are also classified according to the public law status of their activities:
- civil servants with existing public law status: individuals whose status is influenced by the rules of administrative law;
 - civil servants with no public law status: individuals whose status is influenced exclusively by labour law;
 - direct civil servants: bureaucrats and officials;
 - ordinary civil servants: postal staff, pedagogical staff of state-owned schools, etc.

The civil service, like any other service, has a list of functions and tasks assigned to it by the state. The functions and tasks of the civil service are very important and comprehensive, as all areas of society activities depend on their quality.

The basic task of the civil service is to implement and comply with the Ukraine's Constitution provisions, as well as resolutions of the highest authorities in the country. It is through this task that a high-quality level of governance of the state and its bodies is ensured.

In addition, the civil service is obliged to comply with the requirements for the public authorities' effectiveness, which is based on the principles of continuous self-improvement and raising the level of employees' educational qualification. This task becomes especially important when creating new technical, social and legal technologies to ensure transparent and efficient operation of public authorities.

It should be noted that the civil service is responsible for the effective operation of the three branches of government i.e. legislative, executive and judicial.

In today's world, the civil service is committed to a process of gradual eradication of bureaucracy, corruption and other illegal acts. To this end, various bodies are created in Ukraine with different amounts of competencies and powers, such as: National Anti-Corruption Bureau of Ukraine (NABU), National Agency on Corruption Prevention (NACP), State Bureau of Investigation (SBI), Supreme Anti-Corruption Court (SACC) and others.

In addition to the above-mentioned tasks, the public service is entrusted with certain functions which determine its role and direct appointment in society.

The civil service functions are the public authorities' activities, which are aimed at information, legal, personnel, scientific and social security of the population. By performing the civil service functions, the state has the opportunity to improve various areas, get rid of gaps in them, as well as to determine the main directions of the civil service further development in Ukraine.

For a long time of existing the concept of civil service and its functions, scientists have divided them into a certain list of categories by the influence sphere and purpose [5].

The law-making function of the civil service involves the regulatory legal acts creation and improving the quality of the current legislative system.

The political function of the civil service involves the public policy implementation, which is created and approved by the Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine and the President of Ukraine.

The organizational function of the civil service involves the civil service improvement, structuring and systematization, as well as further support of the established system on the basis of law and order.

The regulatory function of the civil service involves the regulation of all public activity spheres, the creation of various government programmes, as well as the policies development for their implementation

Provision and restoration functions of the civil service include the implementation, support and protection of human rights and freedoms of a Ukraine's citizen.

The coercive function of the civil service presupposes the need to apply state coercion in situations provided by law.

The controlling function of the civil service involves overseeing the state's management processes.

There is also another classification of the civil service functions, according to which they can be:

- basic: the most typical functions of the civil service, which are designed to coordinate the interaction between public authorities;
- specific: the civil service functions, involving the intervention of public authorities and employees in various spheres of society, as well as the use of state coercion in cases defined within law;
- auxiliary: the civil service functions, which are intended for service and information, legal, personnel, technical, scientific and social support of public authorities in Ukraine;
- special: the civil service functions aimed at supplementing other functions in certain cases when the basic or specific functions are insufficient.

In addition to the specific classification of the civil service functions and tasks, there is a classification of its types. The civil service types is the civil service classification according to the form of public authorities activities or according to the specifics of competencies and powers of these authorities. There is no consensus among the scientists in Ukraine on the classification of the civil service types according to the specifics of competencies. Thus, some scholars classify the civil service into: civil and militarized, state and civil, military

and federal, civil, general-functional and specialized, municipal and service in political parties, institutions and establishments. Nowadays the most common types of classification of the civil service are its division into civil and militarized service or into general-functional, civil and specialized [7].

Figure 2. A Civil Servant's Duties
Source: compiled by authors on materials [2].

The civil service is a service of individuals who undertake to perform the powers and general and standard functions of the civil service, who do not have a specialized direction and sectoral differences and specifics.

The civil service examples are: activities in the educational and scientific sphere, medical workers' activities, etc.

The militarized service is a service of individuals whose purpose is to protect the life and create safe conditions for the civilian population, to ensure the state's territorial integrity and to protect its sovereignty in the event of encroachment on it. The militarized service examples are: service in the management of the Armed Forces of Ukraine and other military formations of the state.

The general functional service is a service of individuals who connect their activities with the executive, legislative and representative bodies. The general functional service examples are: service in the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine, service in the Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine and in other bodies subordinated to them.

The specialized service is a service of individuals who work in public authorities with a special status. The specialized service examples are: service in the judiciary, service in the prosecutor's office, service in the security services, customs, tax or diplomatic service etc.

In addition to the above-mentioned civil service division according to the specifics of competencies and powers, science also distinguishes the well-known classification according to the form of public authorities' activities: executive, legislative and judicial branches of government.

An important aspect in the civil service activities is the training process of its employees. The issue of education has always occupied and continues to occupy high places in the criteria lists when hiring civil servants. civil servants' training is the process of providing them with professional knowledge at various qualification levels, such as Bachelor's and Master's degrees, which provide education for further work in the public sector.

The most famous centre for providing education for the civil service in Ukraine is the National Academy for Public Administration under the President of Ukraine in Kyiv and its regional institutes in Odessa, Lviv, Dnipro and Kharkiv. In addition to the above-mentioned educational institutions, education in this area is provided in other higher educational institutions of Ukraine.

At the present stage of civil servants' educational sphere development the following types of professional training in this field are distinguished [8]:

- Master's training is a careful study of the educational and training programme for civil servants by individuals with the aim of further employment in the civil service (specialty 281 "Public administration");
- professional upgrade is an improvement of previously acquired skills and knowledge by civil servants in order to improve their professional activity and continuous maintenance of the educational training level;

- internship is the activity that involves civil servants gaining new professional experience and gaining practical skills and knowledge in the specialty. This process usually lasts from one to six months and can take place both within the government body in which the employee works on a permanent basis and in other public authorities [9];
- self-education is the self-acquisition process of professional skills and knowledge, which can be performed by a civil servant in parallel with his/her work activity or other measures to improve the educational level.

Figure 3. Types of the Civil Service According to the Specifics of Competencies and Powers
 Source: compiled by the authors on the basis [6]

Civil servants' professional upgrade is an extremely important process for the state, the purpose of which is to ensure civil servants' effective operation by providing them with certain professional knowledge and skills [10].

Table 1. Specialists' Training in the Public Administration Sphere

Specialists' training of the appropriate educational and qualification level of the specialist, Master's degree in specialties aimed at professional activity in the civil service	
Is carried out	According to the relevant educational and professional programmes
Provides	In-depth legal, economic, politological, managerial, socio-humanitarian, psychological and pedagogical, professional and other types of training necessary for normative-legal, organizational – management and consultative support of the authorities activity the covered by the Law "On Civil Service" [2]
Educational and professional programs are developed by higher educational institutions of the 4th accreditation level in accordance with the requirements of civil servants' professional qualification characteristics of certain categories of positions and approved by the Ministry of Education on the agreement of the Chief Civil Service	
Educational and professional training programmes for Masters' degree in Public Administration, implemented by the Academy of Public Administration, are developed and approved by the Academy of Public Administration	
Individuals who have successfully passed the state certification for education of the appropriate educational and qualification level, receive an academic certificate in a state-approved format	

Source: compiled by authors on materials [2, 8].

The Main Civil Service of Ukraine creates a list of educational institutions for civil servants' advanced training. This list is formed on the basis of competitive selection, which is carried out on the basis of educational programmes accreditation of various higher educational institutions of the country.

Civil servants' educational process is sponsored by:

- organizations and enterprises;
- funds from the state budget;
- other sources that are not prohibited by Ukrainian legislature.

Any funds received by a higher education institution should be directed purely to the educational process of a person in the form of a civil servant, i.e. for the intended purpose. If a certain amount of funds remains in the end

result, they are not subject to withdrawal. Unused funds must remain in the institution for the next academic year.

Among the methods of civil servants' professional upgrade that are currently known to the Ukrainian reality, the following should be emphasized:

- the method of civil servants' training according to vocational education programmes aimed at professional upgrade;
- the method of self-study, which does not include using educational programmes and higher education institutions involvement;
- the method of attending permanent seminars on certain topics. Seminars are developed by educational institutions and approved by authorized authorities. The term of such training is not limited, as it depends on the programme plan of educational activities.
- the method of internship in public authorities of Ukraine or abroad in order to gain new practical experience. After completing the internship, a civil servant is obliged to submit a report on it

The main direction of civil servants' professional upgrade is to update already acquired skills and knowledge. Every person who has connected his/her life with the civil service should take a refresher course at least once every five years [11-12]. At the same time, public sector specialists who hold a position for the first time and have no previous experience are obliged to take this course at the end of the first year of their service.

Conclusions

Based on the abovementioned material, certain conclusions can be drawn. The civil service is a professional activity that involves public reporting and is aimed at solving problems and fulfilling the tasks and functions assigned to the state. The civil service executors are civil servants who are individuals with the appropriate level of education and skills, which, in turn, are improved with the acquisition of practical experience and a course of professional upgrade.

In addition to the direct executors, the civil service has its own classification according to the specifics of competencies, form of activity etc. Among the civil service types are those that are most often used by scientists: civil service, militarized service, general-functional and specialized services.

No less important issue than the civil service classification is the issue of civil servants' education, training, retraining and professional upgrade. Currently in Ukraine there are vocational education programmes of higher education institutions, a variety of seminars for civil servants, as well as the possibility of internships within and outside Ukraine. All this has an impact on the civil service development, its activities and gradual improvement. As the training process for civil servants is continuous and non-exclusive, this improvement has no limitations.

But despite the diversity of professional upgrade methods for civil servants, Ukraine still needs innovations and extraordinary approaches to improve this process. Based on the rapid society development, the methods listed in the article will soon become obsolete and irrelevant. That is why one of the main directions of the implemented administrative reform of Ukraine should be the creation of a new system of professional upgrade of civil service members' activities.

Abstract

This article examines the civil service issue, defines this term definition and its derived concept of a civil servant. The methods of civil servants' professional upgrade in Ukraine are listed, as well as the issue of obtaining education for future activities in government agencies. The classification of civil service types is considered. The main list of functions and tasks assigned to the civil service is indicated.

The aim of the article is a thorough study of professional upgrade methods in the public sector activities, the definition of basic concepts such as civil service and a civil servant, as well as acquaintance with the variety of civil service functions and its types. The article aims to clearly delineate the methods of civil servants' training, as well as to explore methods of further improving their professional skills.

Civil service is a professional activity that involves public reporting and is aimed at solving problems and fulfilling the tasks and functions assigned to the state. This activity is regulated by law and has defined and clear limits of authority. The range of tasks assigned to the civil service is quite extensive. This is due to the fact that its impact affects many areas of society. The civil service has its own values. A civil servant is a person who is a citizen of Ukraine and holds a position in a public authority. Article 4 of the Law of Ukraine "On Civil Service" defines a certain list of principles that a civil servant must adhere to. The civil service is responsible for the effective operation of the three branches of government, i.e. legislative, executive and judicial.

The civil service types is a classification of civil service according to the form of public authorities activities or according to the specifics of competencies and powers of these authorities

An important aspect in the civil service activities is the process of training its employees. Civil servants' training is the process of providing them with professional knowledge at various qualification levels, such as Bachelor's and Master's degrees, which provide education for further work in the public sector. Currently in Ukraine there are vocational education programmes of higher education institutions, a variety of seminars for civil servants, as well as the possibility of internships within and outside Ukraine.

But despite the diversity of training methods for civil servants, Ukraine still needs innovations and extraordinary approaches in order to improve this process. Based on the rapid society development, the methods listed in the article will soon become obsolete and irrelevant. That is why one of the main directions of the implemented administrative reform of Ukraine should be the creation of a new system of professional upgrade of civil service members' activities.

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